

9-Month Report 2020

JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR

Responsible Partner: AGES, INSA

Contributing partners: all WP leaders and deputy leaders

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JRP/JIP Report	9 Month Report Y3 (2020)																		
Join Research / Integrative Project	JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR																		
JRP/JIP Leader	Werner Ruppitsch																		
Other contributors	Adriana Cabal (2-AGES), Manuela Caniça (36-INSA), Karin Rainer (2-AGES), Krista Rathhammer (2-AGES), and all WP leaders and deputy leaders within FED-AMR.																		
Due month of the deliverable	30																		
Actual submission month	6																		
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 1 October 2020																		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>This is the default setting. If this deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):</i>																		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<table style="width: 100%; border: none;"> <tr> <td>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td>Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>National Stakeholders / Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>ECDC <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> </tr> </table> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>		National Stakeholders / Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/>			EFSA <input type="checkbox"/>	ECDC <input type="checkbox"/>	
OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>																	
OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																		
Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>																		
National Stakeholders / Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/>																			
EFSA <input type="checkbox"/>	ECDC <input type="checkbox"/>																		

1. Summary of the work carried out in the JRP

In the FED-AMR project, extracellular DNA (exDNA) is presented as an important environmental reservoir for antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs). Furthermore, bacterial transformation contributes to the horizontal gene transfer (HGT) of antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs). However, empirical data on the impact of bacterial transformation in the environment are lacking.

Since the beginning of the project on 1st January 2020, and to fulfil its aims, we are conducting a longitudinal study over a one-year crop-growing period by monitoring and comparing 11 different matrices (“Compartments”) from agricultural research areas (or alternatively, from production units) located in four European regions. Indeed, the FED-AMR project aims are 1) to analyse microbial biodiversity and ARGs along food/feed chain, 2) to evaluate the relevance of free exDNA in the HGT of ARGs over ecosystem boundaries 3) to identify points for intervention to reduce the spread of AMR via exDNA 4) to compare geographical differences and trends in AMR and antimicrobials in the natural environment 5) to put a focus on multidrug and emerging resistances.

Overall, we have been able to coordinate the sampling (WP1) and generate all sampling protocols (WP2) for the 11 compartments, the general culture protocol (WP2) and the *C. difficile* culture protocol (WP3), as well as the three protocols for analysis of antibiotics, elements and herbicides in environmental samples (WP4). Also, we finalized the description of the catchment areas and collectors within the four European regions (WP2), the guidelines for sample distribution, transportation and conservation (WP2), the sampling timeline for each collector (WP2) and the unified sample references (WP2). In addition, protocols including extracellular DNA extraction, Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) of bacterial isolates and shotgun metagenomics are finished as well. The only protocol that is under discussion to be able to complete D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1 is the qPCR protocol, since the planned budget for metagenomics can be tight, and therefore we are considering to divert funds to metagenomics and obtain quantitative data rather than using qPCR.

All FED-AMR partners have been affected by COVID-19 as many have been directly involved in the work and laboratory activities, which have been shut down to handle only essential work. Additionally, in many cases, sample collection, laboratory work and analysis of the samples were delayed, as well as the recruitment of post-doctoral fellows, PhD students or technicians. However, very recently, 10-FLI and 13-SSI have recruited a PhD student each (Ines Dost and Semeh Bejaoui, respectively), 25-NUIG and 36-INSA a MSc student each (Charitini Nikolaidou and Rita Castro, respectively). Likewise, a PhD student (Krõõt Arbo) and two technicians (Jelena Kiprovskaia and Viia Kõiv) have been recruited by 14-UTARTU. Two Postdocs (Marwa Hassan and Brian Gardner, respectively) are already integrated and learnt about the FED-AMR project at 23-UoS.

Finally, many other projects and tasks from OHEJP projects have been delayed and the new plans for their execution will take place differently as initially foreseen, which may affect the timeline of the FED-AMR work (laboratory, data analysis and results dissemination).

Also, as described in WP1 and WP2 (see corresponding WPs below), the huge amount of experimental and sampling protocols needed exceeded the expectations. However, for these and all WPs, we are committed to make good use of the time lost in order to compensate the delay in milestones and deliverables. Nevertheless, all partners hope that the period of the project can be extended after June 2022, as this will help in weighting decisions, in more detailed analysis of results and in a greater dissemination, so that the project can have an improved impact on decision makers.

2. Progress of the project: description of activities

All WPs have started, but with delays in one or several tasks. Additional information on the progress can be found below for each task and subtask in the different WPs. As the recruitment of the last fellows has not happened until recently we will only be able to adjust all budget changes in December

for the FED-AMR Annual Report, due to changes in several tasks of the project.

WP1: Project Management and Communication (M25-M54)

AGES is responsible for the project management and for all communication within FED-AMR (WP1). The leader of the WP1 is now Werner Ruppitsch and his deputy leader is Adriana Cabal Rosel.

JRP15-WP1-T1: Scientific Management (M25-M54)

Manuela Caniça (36-INSA) is now the responsible person for the scientific management of the project, acting as leader of task 1 within this WP (**WP1-T1**). She is supported by her deputy leader Adriana Cabal Rosel (2-AGES). This task is **ongoing** and it will comprise the whole project duration (M25 to M54). Up to now, this task together with task **WP1-T2** has involved the creation of a Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) composed by experts within the consortium and the nomination of the local administrative representatives. The outcome of both tasks can be seen as part of the deliverable D-JRP15-FED-AMR - WP1.1 (before named as D-JRP17-FED-AMR -WP1.1).

A risk management strategy is being implemented and it is intended to be regularly updated by the Administrative Manager (Karin Rainer, 2-AGES) and the Scientific Manager (Manuela Caniça, 36-INSA), to ensure that adverse situations are properly handled along the course of the project.

JRP15-WP1-T1.1: Coordination of sampling, laboratory experiments and building a database (M25-M33)

Manuela Caniça (36-INSA) is now the responsible person for this **ongoing** sub-task, and her sub task deputy leader Adriana Cabal Rosel (2-AGES) supports her. Initially, this subtask was planned to start in M25 and to finish in M28. The task started on the expected month (M25), but it will end now in M33. This is partially due to SARS-CoV-2 crisis that prevented many partners to hire staff, work in the laboratory or coordinating sampling campaigns.

The deliverable associated to this sub-task (now named as D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP1.2) was delayed as well because it is strongly associated with WP2 and its corresponding deliverable D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1. Both deliverables are expected by M33.

Contributing partners collaborated to generate new guidelines and harmonized protocols for sampling and experimental analysis. The high number of newly designed protocols exceeded the initial expectations and contributed to this delay, even when using some available from the EFFORT project, as well as from COMPARE and from reference institutions (e.g. DTU in Denmark), as foreseen. Those protocols included sampling protocols for 11 compartments, protocols for the molecular techniques, or culture protocols, among others.

In this sub-task (WP1-T1.1), the leader and the deputy leader, coordinated the sampling and the experimental protocols. Within the sampling, project partners were asked about the type of samples they could collect. As stated in the proposal, 11 different compartments were proposed for each European Region. However, not all partners could collect samples from each of the compartments. Most of the experimental protocols have been finished, but those related to genomics are finishing in M33. For additional information, see WP2.

JRP15-WP1-T1.2: Webinar forum and Skype meetings for instant scientific interactions (M30-M50)

Task WP1-T1.2 is **ongoing** and two webinars were already held. The first webinar on the topic “Environmental reservoirs of antimicrobial resistance genes” took part of the deliverable related to this task (D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP1.4), which took place in M31. Professor Elisabeth Wellington was proposed as the first speaker. The second webinar was celebrated in M33 and it collected information about the first metagenomics and gene enrichment tests carried out with samples from the FED-AMR project. For the third webinar, which will take place in M33, the WP leader proposed Markus

Wögerbauer as speaker and moderator.

Regarding the online meetings, the vast majority of project partners have attended through a different online platform other than Skype at the beginning of each month, since the kick off meeting. Minutes of the meetings were registered and shared with the project partners for approval. A definitive version incorporating all suggestions received was distributed and published in the AGES site (<https://fed-amr.ages.at>). In addition, weekly calls were arranged between the deputy leader of WP1 and the leader of WP1-T1.1 to discuss the evolution of the different WPs and tasks.

JRP15-WP1-T1.3: Project Meetings (M25-M52)

The Kick off meeting took place in Vienna at the end of the M25. The next one is planned in Lisbon in M41. This task is **ongoing**.

JRP15-WP1-T2: Administrative Management (M25-M54)

The administrative management (AM) is supported by the infrastructure of the AGES academy and the secretariat of the AGES knowledge transfer department. The coordination of joint activities in the frame of the FED-AMR project is being coordinated by AGES. Additionally, each partner had appointed an Administrative Representative who is and will be in direct contact with the AGES Administrative Manager (AM) whenever necessary. A risk management strategy for the project is being put in place by the Administrative Manager (AM) and the Scientific Manager (SM), in consultation with the Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) to ensure that adverse situations are properly handled along the course of the project, which will be highlighted in the Data Management Plan. This task is **ongoing**.

JRP15-WP1-T3: Data and Protocol Management (M25-M52)

The Data and Protocol Management Plan has been delayed and therefore, its deliverable is expected by M34. DMP leader attended online training on August 5th 2020 for the new OHEJP data management platform CDP, provided by the OHEJP WP4 team. The CDP application will be adapted and updated with details of FED-AMR data throughout the project, with information provided to the leader and deputy leader by task leaders on their datasets. This task is **ongoing**.

WP2: Field experiments: Determination of the naturally occurring ARG background load and microbial biodiversity in the tested environmental compartments (M25-M50)

WP2 takes place over the first, second and third year of the project (Y3, Y4 and Y5) after the end of the project have been delayed to M50. Thus, Tasks WP2-T1. and WP2-T2. take place in the first year (Y3). Tasks WP2-T3, and WP2-T4. take place over the first and second year of the project (Y3 and Y4). Tasks WP2-T5. and WP2-T6. take place over the second year (Y4). Task WP2-T7 was delayed up to the third year, so now is planned to take place over the three years of the project (Y3, Y4 and Y5).

Overall, in this WP the prevalence, quantity and movement of AMR via free exDNA will be monitored along different compartments of the food/feed chain within the HOAL catchment: "human/animal gut -> manure -> soil -> crop -> drainage -> surface water -> groundwater -> human/animal". All matrices (pig faeces, manure, agricultural soil, crop plants, drainage, surface and ground-water) will be analysed for the presence of clinically relevant ARGs encoded on free exDNA taking into special account antimicrobial treatments of the pig herds. Cultivable, resistant soil and gut bacteria will be characterized with standard microbiological methods. The results will be compared with data obtained from similar testing locations and environmental compartments from different regions. The establishment of the bacterial biodiversity in the tested compartments will be carried out, as well as the identification of the most prevalent naturally transformable species in agricultural soils and the monitoring of their fate in different environmental compartments.

JRP15-WP2-T1: Assemble list of sampling compartments and points. Determination of test areas representative for the European regions (North, West, East, South) (M25-M30)

The consortium members contributed to compile the final list of sampling compartments and points, having been carried out according to the collectors from East (Czech Republic, Poland), West (Austria, Ireland and Great Britain), North (Estonia and Norway), and South (Portugal). The final list of compartments according to partners was achieved and is already available to the participants via the AGES site (<https://fed-amr.ages.at>), as well as the sample timeline by collectors, the sample distribution, transport and conservation of sampling by compartment. A unique identifier by compartment and time point was given to all samples planned to be collected in the frame of the FED-AMR project, ensuring a correct traceability of all samples from their collection until their processing and analysis at the laboratory. The description of the HOALs and main catchment areas within FED-AMR was elaborated. Participants of WP2 (2-AGES, 7-SZU, 14-UT, 23-UoS, 25-NUIG, 33-NVI, 36-INSA) provided input and advice according to their expertise and involvement in the sampling. The sampling list provided in this task supports harmonization of testing procedures and enhances comparability of the results obtained from those regions of Europe. As the leader and deputy leader of this task changed being actually 2-AGES and 36-INSA, they provided preparatory and final work, and the remaining participants took part, namely during the teleconferences made monthly by the project leader with all from the consortium. End month was delayed to 30. This task is **finished**.

JRP15-WP2-T2: Establish common protocol for sampling and data analyses to facilitate comparability of the results between European test areas (North, West, East, South) and local sampling locations (M25-M33)

Common protocols for sample collection were made available by the leader and the new deputy leader; it is finished later than planned (end month M33) due to the number of compartments and procedures and in view of the participants 2-AGES, 7-SZU, 14-UT, 23-UoS, 25-NUIG, 33-NVI, 36-INSA being more directly involved. At present, all compartments already have the respective protocols of sampling, which were uploaded on AGES site (<https://fed-amr.ages.at>) for FED-AMR, available for all partners. The protocols of culture are also available and provide a harmonizing framework in the microbiology laboratory, for the isolation, detection and identification of specific bacterial isolates from different samples collected, such as faeces (from pigs, wild animals and farmers), manure, soil, water, crops and feed. This procedure applies to bacterial isolates that may have human, veterinary, zoonotic or environmental bacteria, in such samples, focusing on six species (*Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella* spp, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecium* and *E. faecalis*). Since joining the project in April, one 23-UoS Postdoc has been engaged in helping revising those protocols in which UoS is involved under WP2, e.g. pig feces, manure and culture, and in writing the susceptibility testing protocol, which is an example of cooperation of the partners in this task. The protocol for DNA extractions (eDNA and Total DNA) was finished for samples of all compartments (pig and wild animals feces, and feces from farmers, manure, soil, crops, river water, groundwater, wastewater and feed). The protocols for genomics are finished by the respective task and deputy task leader (see task WP2-T3; WP2-T3.2 and WP2-T4). The only protocol that is under discussion to be able to complete D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1. is the qPCR protocol, since the planned budget for metagenomics can be tight, we are considering to divert funds to metagenomics and obtain quantitative data rather than using qPCR.

These common protocols support harmonization of testing procedures and enhance comparability of the results obtained from different regions of Europe; those protocols already concluded are available via the AGES site (<https://fed-amr.ages.at/home/>) for FED-AMR and under the members area in the OHEJP website (<https://onehealthjep.eu>). 36-INSA and 2-AGES provided preparatory work; the remaining participants provided input and advice according to their expertise and take part in voting and the final decision. This task is finishing in M33.

JRP15-WP2-T3: Assess microbial and ARG diversity with NGS in the selected test environments (metagenomics). Compare microbial and ARG diversity between ecosystems and over ecosystem boundaries. Characterization of cultivable environmental bacteria on complete nutrient and minimal media (M27-M48)

JRP15-WP2-T3.1 Shot gun sequencing and bioinformatic analyses of AMR genes and MGEs

We don't have enough work performed in this subtask according to the protocols that are missing (see task WP2-T2). Even that, the harmonized protocols already decided in **WP2-T1** and **WP2-T2** are using different samples interconnected with several environmental compartments during over a crop growing period of one year, so results will be achieved during this period and end by M48. This task is **ongoing**.

JRP15-WP2-T3.2: Gene enrichment with gene capture probes (M31-M42)

This subtask is being evaluated regarding the pros and cons to do it in terms of achieving better results in metagenomics, as samples with complex communities and various sources of DNA (e.g. soil) need to be well thought out to take decision. For this a pilot and QC studies are being processed between AGES and an enterprise to help on the decision according to the results obtained. The start of this task was delayed to M31.

JRP15-WP2-T4: Quantify clinically relevant ARGs in the tested compartments (qPCR; qPCR arrays) (M34-M42)

ARG qPCRs protocol was planned to be performed. However, since the planned budget for metagenomics may be too tight, we are considering diverting funds to metagenomics and obtain quantitative data from it instead of by using qPCR. A member of the Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) is contributing with 2-AGES for this decision. If performed, the start of this task will be delayed to M34.

JRP15-WP2-T7: Isolate and assess quantity, diversity and stability of free extracellular ARG encoding DNA in the tested environments. Sequence comparisons (M34-M50)

The start and end of this task were delayed to M34 and M50 (in year 5), respectively.

WP3: Elucidating the role of Clostridium difficile as an ARG transfer platform over ecosystems boundaries and its linkage between human and non-human (zoonotic) reservoirs (M25-M50)

There is increasing evidence that *C. difficile* may have a foodborne or zoonotic aetiology, challenging the One Health paradigm. *C. difficile* has also been suggested as a reservoir/receptor of resistance genes that might be transferred to other species in the host gut as well as in the environment. WP3 aims therefore to investigate the epidemiology of zoonotic *C. difficile*, the genetic overlap between human and non-human *C. difficile* lineages and the role of *C. difficile* as an ARG transfer platform over ecosystems boundaries.

JRP15-WP3-T1 - Epidemiological survey of zoonotic ribotypes across participant countries. (M25-M40)

In M25 a first survey was carried out among the six WP3 participating partners, regarding available *C. difficile* strains, sources of these strains, year of isolation and available phenotypic and AMR data.

All involved partners have at the moment *C. difficile* strains that can be already integrated into the project, despite they will need to be complemented with isolates from other sources. Therefore, the possibility to collect new isolates from different sources was also evaluated, and the majority of the partners gave a positive response. Therefore the existing collection will be enriched in order to meet a One Health frame. Due to COVID-19 pandemic, the collection of new isolates is forecasted to start in

M34. We are currently identifying in human *C. difficile* strains, the most likely zoonotic ribotypes. WP3 team has also prepared a harmonized protocol for *C. difficile* isolation and characterization from fecal, soil and water samples, to be applied in WP3, T3.4. This task is **ongoing**.

JRP15-WP3-T2 - WGS and AMR characterization of human and non-human C. difficile isolates (M34-M46)

In normal conditions, this task should start in M31, but due to COVID-19 pandemics, its start will be delayed to M34.

WP4: Determination of the selection pressures in the tested compartments of human, animal and environmental ecosystems (M25-M50)

Due to the COVID-19 crisis, the start of tasks WP4-T2 to WP4-T7 was delayed. The main reason was the impossibility of shipping samples to the laboratory performing the analysis (34-PIWET), due to national COVID-19 restrictions. Meanwhile, 128 samples from HOAL Austria were shipped on 22th June and 1st September 2020 to 34-PIWET (antibiotics), UBA Vienna (herbicides) and 23-UoS (elements), after the creation of a detailed list of shipping companies. All other samples will be shipped from other HOALs between September and October 2020. If everything goes according to the plan, analyses of the first set of collected samples of soil (WP4-T5), manure (WP4-T3) and water (WP4-T2) will be done by the end of September.

JRP15-WP4-T1 Selection of essential antimicrobials to be quantified in the tested compartments (published antibiotic consumption data, farmers' questionnaire, personal experience, expert interviews (veterinarians) (M25-M30)

This task is **finished**. Task WP4-T1, was planned for M25 to M26. The task was delayed, but it has been finished in M30 and the corresponding deliverable (D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP4.1) was uploaded into the members area of the OHEJP website; this deliverable contains three protocols as annexes on the quantification of antibiotics, elements and herbicides in the different compartments.

Corresponding to the ARGs (*tet(M)*, *tet(W)*, *tet(Z)*, *sul1*, *sul2*, *sul3*, *erm*-like genes, PMQR-encoding genes) to be investigated in the environment (faeces, manure, agricultural soil, drainage, surface and ground-water; see WP2), the four antimicrobial classes to be tested in these compartments were selected: tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones (task JRP15-WP4-T1). From these antibiotic groups the most important (according to published antibiotic consumption data and EFSA report on antibiotic residues in live animals and food) were included in the analytical method by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC/MSMS) performed by 34-PIWET (WP4-T2 to WP4-T5).

Herbicides were chosen in the same Task, among those that are often used in agriculture, such as glufosinate and glyphosate, as well as its degradation product aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA), 2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D). Quantification of these substances (Task WP4-T6) will be performed by an AGES associated sister company (UBA Vienna).

Heavy metals and trace elements were also already chosen among those that are triggering co-selection and that have been used in co-selection studies: Cd, Cr, Cu, Ni, Hg, Co, Pb, Zn. The samples will be analysed by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP/MS) carried out by 23-UoS (Task WP4-T7).

JRP15-WP4-T2 Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in aqueous matrices (water) (M31-M50)

Samples from some HOALs were taken and collected: 5 water samples from different compartments including wastewater (inlet and outlet), river water, ground water and drainage water.

Due to the COVID-19 crisis, the start of tasks WP4-T2 to WP4-T7 has been delayed. The main reason

was the impossibility of sending samples to the laboratory performing the analysis, due to national COVID-19 restrictions. Meanwhile, 10 samples from HOAL Austria were shipped on 22th June and 1st September 2020. If everything goes according to plan, analyses of these first set of collected samples will be done by the end of September. The expected starting date for this task was M27, but it has been delayed to M31 (M-JRP15-FED-AMR-31 to -36, except -32).

JRP15-WP4-T3 Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in manure (M31-M50)

The expected starting date for this task was M27. The start date for analyses is now M31 (see task WP4-T2). However, samples from some HOALs were already collected. 4 samples from HOAL Austria were shipped on 22th June and 1st September 2020. Other HOALs will ship samples in September 2020.

JRP15-WP4-T4 Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in faeces (M35-M50)

The expected starting date for this task was M30. The new starting date is delayed to M35.

JRP15-WP4-T5 Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in soil (M31-M50)

The expected starting date for this task was M27. The start date for analyses is delayed to M31 (see task WP4-T2). Samples from some HOALs have been already collected. 28 soil samples from HOAL Austria were shipped on 22th June and 1st September 2020. Other HOALs will ship samples from September 2020 onwards.

JRP15-WP4-T6 Quantification of herbicides in agricultural soil (M31-M50)

The expected starting date for this task was M27. The start date for analyses is delayed to M31 (see task WP4-T2).

Samples from some HOALs were collected. 41 samples (28 soil, 3 manure, 10 water) from HOAL Austria were shipped on 22th June and 1st September 2020. Other HOALs will ship samples from September 2020 onwards.

JRP15-WP4-T7 Measurement of the concentration of trace elements in environmental samples gathered across participants countries (M31-M50)

Since the start of the project, the work has been done in order to design a sampling strategy suitable for the analysis of trace elements in variety of samples. These include soils, crops and animal feed, water, manure and sewage sludge. The researchers have worked very closely with the leaders of WP2 in order to harmonize the sampling strategy and make sure that the sampling procedures and processing were compatible with all types of analyses across the consortium. The team has also completed the protocol for sample preparation for solid and liquid samples, as well as the procedures for instrumental analysis and the sourcing of the certified reference material for validation. Arrival of the first set of samples to the ICP-MS Facility at Surrey was planned for March 2020, however this was postponed due to the lock-down and restrictions to research activities at the University of Surrey, starting on 23rd March. The labs have started to reopen gradually since June, and after assessing the risk posed by COVID-19 epidemics, the 1st set of samples is expected to be completed by the end of September 2020.

Samples from HOALs have been already taken, namely at the Austrian HOAL, where 21 soil, 5 water, 2 manure and 2 feed samples were collected. 45 samples (28 soil, 3 manure, 10 water, 3 feed, 1 crop) from HOAL Austria were shipped on 22th June and 1st September 2020. Other HOALs will ship samples from September 2020 onwards.

The expected starting date for this task was M27. The start date for analyses was delayed to M31.

WP5: Identification of environmental conditions modulating transformation frequencies in soil microcosms and an in vitro porcine gut model (poGutMo) (laboratory studies) (M32-M52)

The start of this work package has been delayed for two reasons. First, it took longer than anticipated for 23-UoS to recruit the PDRA to work on this work package. Second, the laboratories at 23-UoS have been closed due to national COVID-19 restrictions since March. Marwa Hassan was recruited successfully to the project at the end of April 2020. In the second week of June, the first members of staff have begun a phased return to the laboratories. M. Hassan was able to access the laboratories early in July. From mid-June, she has focussed on preparing the protocols and ordering the consumables to start work on WP5 in M32. This represents a seven-month delay to the anticipated start of WP5. As such, WP5-T1 will now be extended into year 4, as will WP5-T1-ST3 and WP5-T1-ST4. We anticipate getting the project back on track by M45.

Acinetobacter was proposed as a model organism for transformation experiments; however, our preliminary experiments proved the inability of this pathogen to grow anaerobically. After consultation with the team and FEM-AMR consortium, we are going to perform the transformation experiments using *E. coli* as a model organism in the anaerobic gut model. Currently, the selection of strains to use for the transformation and conjugation experiments has started. *E. coli* J53 (a derivative of K-12) and 912 (isolated from pigs) will be kindly provided by AGES and Ana Herrero-Fresno (University of Copenhagen), respectively, to be used for the transformation experiments. For the conjugation experiments, *C. difficile* strains 630 and CD37 will be kindly provided by Prof. Peter Mullany, University College London, in the near future. A further investigation is still ongoing to identify other potential isolates to use in the pig gut model. We are currently finalising the protocols and involved risk assessments for WP5, including procedures for analysis of trace elements and heavy metals in samples from the pig gut model.

JRP15-WP5-T1 Establish baseline levels of HGT in the model organism (*E. coli*) arising from transformation in the poGutMo (M32-M45).

Preliminary experiments proved the inability of *Acinetobacter* to grow anaerobically; thus, *E. coli* was chosen as a model organism for the transformation experiments in the anaerobic gut model.

Start date delayed to M32. New end month: 45.

JRP15-WP5-T1-ST1 Ability of *E. coli* strains to acquire AMR to serve as a donor DNA (M34-M36).

Start date delayed to M34. New end month: 36.

JRP15-WP5-T1-ST2 Determine the optimal growth parameters for cultivating *E. coli* strains within the gut model (M36-M39).

Start date delayed to M36. New month: 39 (Year 4).

JRP15-WP5-T1-ST3 Rates of transformation calculated by taking samples from the gut model and plating on TSC agar plates supplemented with the appropriate antibiotics (M41-M45).

Start date delayed to M41. New end month: 45 (Year 4).

JRP15-WP5-T1-ST4 DNA transfer rates via bacterial conjugation will be calculated using the endpoint method (M34-M45).

Start date delayed to M34. New end month: 45 (Year 4).

WP 6: Probabilistic and mechanistic models of the links between antimicrobial usage in animals, AMR in the environment, and the risks for public health (M32-M54)

The start of this work package has been delayed as it took longer than anticipated for 23-UoS to recruit the PDRA to work on this work package. A Postdoc (Brian Gardner) was recruited successfully to the project at the beginning of May. Thus, the project and milestones were delayed by two months.

JRP15-WP6-T1 Build a probabilistic mathematical model of the emergence of AMR in target bacteria and the relative contribution of transformation and conjugation to ARG acquisition (M32-M54).

Gardner has started to define the protocol for a systematic search of the literature on environment and AMR. The output of the search will also provide the data to be used as input for the machine learning approach. An initial preliminary search returned about 3000 papers, and we are now finalizing the protocol and inviting other members of the team to start the review. As Barnaghi has recently resigned from the University, Mirek Bober has agreed to help with WP6-T1, mentoring Brian Gardner and advising the group.

JRP15-WP6-T1-ST1 Data Integration, Annotation and Association Analysis (M32-M37)

Start date delayed to M32.

JRP15-WP6-T2 - Develop mechanistic models to address key questions regarding the spatio-temporal changes observed in microbiological communities (M32-M54)

Since May, Gardner has been fully engaged in reviewing the relevant literature. He has been in contact with team in UoS (Chambers, La Ragione, Horton and other members of their group) to explore different sources of data that can be used as input/validation for the modelling approach and to refine the research questions. He is also exploring different modelling approaches (e.g. agent-based model) relevant to the task.

JRP15-WP6-T2.1 - Modelling microbial communities I (M34-M41)

Start date delayed to M34.

3. Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JRP code	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name <i>Original name, if different from the actual one</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 10)</i>
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR - WP1.1	Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) installed. Local administrative representatives nominated (T1, T2)	M25	M25		Confidential (contains e-mail addresses of the members of the consortium)	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR - WP1.2	Unified sampling and experimental protocols (T1.1.)	M27		M33	Public	2
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR - WP1.3	Data and protocol management plan (T3)	M27		M34	Public	8
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR - WP1.4	Webinars (T1.2.)	M30	M31		Public	5
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR - WP2.1	List of sampling compartments, points and European test areas and harmonized protocols in alignment with EFFORT project protocols available in data repository (T2.1, T2.2)	M26		M33	Public	2

JRP code	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name <i>Original name, if different from the actual one</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 10)</i>
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP4.1	Standardize protocols for sampling and testing of environmental samples	M26	M30		Public	2
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.1	<i>E. coli</i> strains demonstrated to be suitable for transformation	M26		M36	Confidential until published	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.2	Optimal growth parameters for cultivating <i>E. coli</i> within the porcine gut model and the time after inoculation at which its concentration is maximal determined	M27		M39	Confidential until published	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.3	Optimal growth parameters for cultivating the clostridial strains within the gut model determined	M28		M37	Confidential until published	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.4	Results from pilot experiments using PCR amplicons as ARG donors	M30		M43	Confidential until published	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.5	Conjugation-mediated HGT between the clostridial donor and recipient strains within the gut model determined	M31		-M45	Confidential until published	10

JRP code	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name <i>Original name, if different from the actual one</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 10)</i>
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.6	Results from using chromosomal DNA derived from <i>E. coli</i> as ARG donor	M33		M45	Confidential until published	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.1	Main code for the mathematical modelling made available in public repository (e.g. GitHub) with associated documentation (which can be used as "Material and Method" section of the forthcoming publications).	M30		M37	Public	3

* *Categories of Integrative activities (10 options): 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities (response); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify); 9. This is supportive to an integrative activity; 10. This is not an integrative activity*

Milestones

JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-01	Kick off meeting	M26	Yes		
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-02	Database repository active	M27	Yes		
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-03	Webinar forums started	M30	Yes		The consortium initiated the scientific exchange via online teleconferences and formally installed regular webinars by M31.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-07	List of sampling compartments, points and European test areas available. Harmonized protocols for sample collection + transportation, DNA extraction, qPCR, metagenomics, shotgun sequencing, gene capture and bioinformatics and statistical analysis of sequence data available. Alignment with EFFORT project protocols (T2.1, T2.2)	M26	No	M33	The list of sampling compartments, points and European test areas have been defined. Harmonized protocols for sample collection and transportation and DNA extraction protocols are already available for all project members. Protocols for WGS, metagenomics, gene capture and bioinformatics are still under development. When possible, sampling protocols were aligned with e.g. EFFORT project.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-30	Starting the selection of essential antimicrobials to be quantified in the tested	M25	Yes		

JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		compartments				
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-31	Starting the analysis of antimicrobials in aqueous matrices	M27	No	M31	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-32	Starting the analysis of antimicrobials in manure	M31		M31	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-33	Starting the analysis of antimicrobials in faeces	M29	No	M31	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-34	Starting the analysis of antimicrobials in soil	M31			
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-35	Starting the quantification of herbicides in agricultural soil	M31			
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-36	Starting the measurement of the concentration of trace elements in environmental samples	M27		M31	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-37	Bacterial strains supplied to UoS	M25		M34	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-38	Porcine gut model set up using faecal samples obtained through WP2, samples stored for trace	M26		M40	

JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		element analysis (WP4) – experiments can start				
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-39	Samples from gut model experiments stored for trace element analysis (WP4)	M30		M41	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-40	Samples from gut model experiments stored for trace element analysis (WP4)	M31		M42	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-41	Samples from gut model experiments stored for trace element analysis (WP4)	M33		M43	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-42	DNA sent for whole-genome sequencing	M33		M44	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-53	Literature review on concept of resilience and modelling in microbial communities.	M27		M34	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-54	Identification of relevant available data. Formulation and implementation of the model for the microbiological community within-host. Conditioned to data availability, potential extension of the model to natural environment (e.g. soil).	M30		M37	

4. *Follow-up of the recommendations and comments by the Ethics Advisors*

Requirements of ethical reviewers in 2020	What measures and actions do you propose?
<p>(1) Human biological samples The beneficiaries must confirm that appropriate authorizations will be sought to collect the Human samples.</p>	<p>The ethical self-assessment was sent out to all partners of the FED-AMR project to ensure besides visibility and awareness of the high demand and principles of ethical conduct, a basic feedback on the mentioned issues relevant for OHEJP and this project. As no critical paths were identified and no current risks for the further progress of FED-AMR became obvious by this first assessment, the digestion and iterative update of the process are running in regular terms. An amended and clean version of the ethics section will be presented in the regular reporting periods. The first re-evaluation (end date 10th September) revealed no further critical paths and can be found in the annex of this report.</p>
<p>(2) personal data processing The beneficiaries must confirm that the personal data will be processed according to GDPR (EU 2016/679), and the contact address of the Data Protector Officer of the institution in charge of processing the data obtained must be provided.</p>	
<p>(3) Animals Further details are need on the use of animals which are legal animals and any experimental animals (i.e. pigs). Please clearly state the 3Rs aspects of this work. Please describe how the beneficiaries are complying with access to animal material requirements and animal welfare laws.</p>	

5. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on the project

Tasks or Subtasks	Milestones and Deliverables						Associated budget		
	Name of Task or Subtask	End date according to AWP 2020	Expected end date due to crisis	Associated Milestone or Deliverable	Deadline according to AWP 2020	New proposed deadline	Reason for delay	Budget that will not be spent	Budget that will be spent with delay
WP1								--	--
WP2						Laboratories closed Staff and resources allocated to COVID testing sample dispatch impaired		--	--
WP3								--	--
WP4								--	--
WP5									
WP5-T1	M36	M45	D-JRP17-FED-AMR-WP5.1	M26	M36	Laboratories closed plus additional technical challenges		-	67,288
WP5-T1-ST1	M27	M36	D-JRP17-FED-AMR-WP5.2	M27	M39				
WP5-T1-ST2	M30	M39	D-JRP17-FED-AMR-WP5.3	M28	M37				
WP5-T1-ST3	M33	M45	D-JRP17-FED-AMR-WP5.4	M30	M43				
WP5-T1-ST4	M36	M5	D-JRP17-FED-AMR-WP5.5	M31	M45				
			D-JRP17-FED-AMR-WP5.6	M33	M45				
			D-JRP17-FED-AMR-WP5.7	M36	M51				

		D-JRP17-FED-AMR-WP5.8	M36	M51		
		M-JRP17-FED-AMR-37	M25	M34		
		M-JRP17-FED-AMR-38	M26	M40		
		M-JRP17-FED-AMR-39	M30	M41		
		M-JRP17-FED-AMR-40	M31	M42		
		M-JRP17-FED-AMR-41	M33	M43		
		M-JRP17-FED-AMR-42	M33	M44		
		M-JRP17-FED-AMR-43	M36	M51		
WP6						--

Comments:

All partners have been affected by COVID-19 as many have been directly involved in the work and laboratory activities have been shut down to handle only essential work. Additionally, in many cases, collection, laboratory work, and result analysis of samples have not been performed during this period (e.g. in WP4: impossibility of sending samples to the laboratory performing the analysis, due to national COVID-19 restrictions). The recruitment of postdocs, PhD and MSc students and technicians for the project needed to be postponed, which considerably delayed the start of various WPs and tasks, and the progress of the project. Finally, many other projects and tasks from OHEJP projects have been delayed and the new plans for their execution will take place differently for the initially planned, which may affect the time line of FED-AMR work (laboratory, data analysis, and results dissemination). Budget can be expected to exceed the initial plan due to these reasons, which will be more correctly evaluated after reviewing the new fellows recruited. The budget not spent during the COVID lockdown and restriction period will be needed at a later date in order to perform the necessary analyses and recruitments. This in turn might lead to higher costs than anticipated, because of the higher administrative complexity and because some sampling rounds could not be performed and had to be postponed.

WP1 as an exception as it was nearly not hampered by the shut down due to mainly desktop work and had on the other hand additional effort by facilitating and finding alternative working ways and resources.

6. *Publications*

Not applicable at the moment.

Additional output

- Abstract describing the FED-AMR project sent to the ASM Annual Meeting, held online on 27th-29th May, 2020 (selected for e-Poster presentation).
- Launch of an internal website hosted by AGES that serves as an exchange platform of internal documents. Partners are granted with private access and can download common protocols, minutes from the TCs and other documents.

7. *Data Management Plan*

1. Have you uploaded a first version of the project's DMP to the DMP group on the OHEJP website?

Not yet, but it is expected by M34. At the Project Leader's Forum we were informed about a tool that will help Project partners to develop easily their DMP, which we expected to be delivered before the end of M31. However, the training was provided by the OHEJP WP4 team on August 5th 2020 for the new OHEJP data management platform CDP; the application is now being adapted with details of FED-AMR data for a first version of DMP, which will be also done throughout all the project, with information provided to the leader and deputy leader by task leaders on their datasets. This task is **ongoing**.

2. Have you encountered any problems or difficulties when setting up and updating the DMP? If yes, please specify.

8 On-going and planned collaborations with national or European projects or networks

There are complementarities between the FED-AMR protocols and those available from EFFORT and COMPARE projects, and some from the DTU National Food Institute, the International Organization for Animal Health (OIE), and also needed information from European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). Several partners of FED-AMR participate in other JRP and JIP projects from OHEJP (e.g. AGES participates in the MedVetKlebs, INSA participates in Matrix, etc).

The synergies between these projects could be established at a later stage, once the project partners within FED-AMR share their first results. The same will apply to possible synergies with EFSA, ECDC, the SSB and POC members.